

**REFORMING THE CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF
WRONGFUL CONVICTIONS IN PAKISTAN**

Moomal Qadir¹, Shah Muhammad Zarkoon^{1*}

¹University Law College, University of Balochistan, Quetta.

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Author info:

Corresponding Author.
Shah Muhammad Zarkoon
smzarkoon@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research paper discussed the main cause behind the wrong conviction, in which the innocent people are punished and considered as guilty for the crime which were not committed by them. This research paper will point out all those causes of such convictions. Some of causes are weak investigation, forced confessions, unreliable evidence, poor use of technology/ forensic science, lack of legal aid, and delay in submission of challan etc. This paper will also discuss the effect of that conviction on individuals, their families and breach of their trust on justice system. This research paper is consisted on different reliable sources like books, reports, case laws, and the comparison of the justice system with the justice system of progressive countries. This research paper suggests about reforms which can overcome the wrong convictions. Bringing betterment in police training, use of scientific tools in investigations, accountability. It needs stronger legal reforms to remove all those obstacles in provision of justice.

INTRODUCTION.

In Wrongful conviction occurs when an innocent is punished without committing any crime. This is very serious issue not just in Pakistan, worldwide as well. These convictions have a great impact on innocent people on their life. These convictions decrease the trust of common people on judicial system of Pakistan. Wrongful Convictions in Pakistan are the reason of flaws of system including misconduct of police, errors in judicial system, lack of usage of technology especially forensic. Police torture prisoners especially those they are from lower class to get confession; the delays of court trial make it more badly. It increases the chances of wrongful convictions in Pakistan.

In many cases people are innocent but due to their financial problems and delay of submission of Challan and delays of hearing, they plead guilty, to get rid of all the problems. They are punished for the crime they never did it or never involve it.

Due to lack of forensic evidence courts rely on eyewitness, sometimes eyewitness mistakenly on intentionally identify the wrong person due to bribe, prejudice or pressure. Even in our lower court it is very common that eyewitness is brought by money. They take money and they appeal for recording of their statement and identification of person wrongly. Unfortunately, there is no punishment on wrong / false recording of statement or identification practically.

In developed countries there are many organizations who acquitted the innocent people from the charge on the bases of finger print technique etc., but unfortunately in our country due to lack of this, it looks almost impossible.

The aim of the study is to highlight the role of police, procedure of court, use of forensic evidence and testimony of witness in wrongful convictions. It will also highlight the faults of all the stages, wheatear it is investigation stage, trial stage or phase after conviction, it will deeply enlighten all of them.

Background Study

The wrongful conviction

The wrongful convictions are global issue, but it is more like found in underdeveloped country due to weak judicial system and flaws of their institutions (Gross et al., 2012). In Pakistan this issue is worst, it stated from investigation of police, it continues during trial and till final judgment there is no such a system where the judgments can be reviewed by the court itself. After conviction there is no clear and reliable trusted tools on which anyone can trust.

The Pakistani Criminal Justice System and Its Flaws

Pakistan's criminal justice system is weak due to large number of cases, which takes a lot of time in management. Case remain pending for years. The role of police is another issue. Police to torture people to get confessions from innocents. Police officers often threatens witnesses, plants evidences to get conviction (Binns et al., 2018). The judiciary also plays its role in wrongful convictions. Judges are not well trained in context of modern techniques of forensic science, the judgments given are mostly on assumptions and external pressure.

Eyewitness Testimony and Misidentification

A major cause of wrongful convictions in Pakistan, as in many countries, is rely on eyewitness testimony. In many criminal cases, eyewitnesses are the primary form of evidence used to convict an individual. However, eyewitness misidentification is one of the leading factors in wrongful

Socioeconomic

The issue is more likely to happen with poor, ethnic minorities and rural population due to not having proper representation. Due to economic issue they are deprived of legal representations. In many cases from arrest to judgments they do not get change of fair trial.

Lack of Forensic Infrastructure

In Pakistan the lack of forensic infrastructure due to lack of funds, lack of skilled staff, management of forensic tools and lack of training too. In Pakistan just in Lahore there is a forensic lab, in rest of cities and provinces there is no forensic laboratory. Cases from all over Pakistan sent to the same lab to get the results. Due to burden of work it may have chances of mistake.

The Case for Reform

It needs reforms in criminal justice system. Reforms should be bringing in institutions to improve their role like police, judiciary and modern technology. There is also need of reform in the mechanism of post-conviction review that courts should review the cases by themselves where doubts are present, or this duty can be provided to independent bodies or commissions. Like in progressive countries.

Significance of the Study

The significance of the research is in understanding of the reasons of wrongful convictions in Pakistan. It also suggests the practical solution which is actionable. (HRCP), State of Human Rights in Pakistan (Annual Report, 2022). The main problem is in institutions, institutions in country are not according to their duties, they added some unimportant things to make their work easy. Like police is subject to create fair trial instead of bring conviction, but due to many compulsions, they do not do their work. In some case they are compelled by their higher authorities to get convictions at any cost. It also highlights the effect of those convictions which will lead the individuals to face socially difficulties, it violates human rights and it will affect the right of individuals as well as society.

Filling a Research Gap

When wrongful convictions occurred in progressive countries of the world, they conducted research and found the real reasons of wrongful convictions. This research is having similar significance to those researches. It will fill the gap, which are the main cause behind those convictions. It will offer the justice seeker to take part and add their efforts.

Impact on Human Rights

These convictions are the straightly violation of human's right not just of an individual. It is just because of failure of system. The humans are deprived of their right of fair trial and freedom and despite of that convicted through wrong methods, which is true violation of not just of Pakistan but also the law of Human Rights. This will bring awareness in people to advocate the misuse of laws through reforms (Constitution of Pakistan 1973).

It will be a small light in darkness for the innocent people convicted wrongly those, they do not have much money to get great legal representation. Bringing awareness in public will pressurize the policy makers to resolve the problem and bring reforms

Social and Legal Reform

The aim of the research is to recommend the policy which is actionable and may help to bring reforms in Criminal Justice system of Pakistan, it will decrease the occurrence of wrongful convictions. For that the first step is to find out the mistakes of the system which facilitate the wrongful conviction like the torture of the police on any individual to get conviction, the lack of forensic infrastructure, weaknesses in judicial inefficiency and misguidance or misidentification of the witness. It needs practical changes which will overcome the problem. This research also recommends to bring reforms in institutions to

improve their performance. It will ensure accountability, and it enhances their capacity of work. It will bring the usage of modern forensic techniques in crime investigations. These reforms will not just enhance the legal system, it will also provide security to innocent individuals and overcome the wrongful convictions.

Improving Public Confidence in the Justice System

The impact of wrongful conviction is the loss of public trust not only on judiciary as well as on all the institutions whom are involved in this conviction. It decreases their trust of fairness of the justice system. Highlighting this will retain their trust, but it is long term positive step which needs consistency.

Global Relevance

This research is significant for all those countries having similar legal and institutional challenges, especially in our region. It will also provide suggestion to all those stakeholders to bring reforms and get rid of problem. It will highlight the root causes of those convictions like corruption lack of access to representation in court, interference of politicians. This research could be used anywhere by international organizations like Human rights, NGO and police makers of other countries. It will decrease not just wrongful conviction, but also promote justice on globe.

Justification of the Study

It is justified on different reason, firstly these wrongful convictions are not just legal concerns but also ethical and social concerns as well.

Widespread Reports of Wrongful Convictions

Recently numerous cases are published of wrongful convictions in Pakistan, where innocents are convicted and sentenced wrongly and later on were released, but they spent many years of their precious time in prison just because of failure of the system. In some cases, the eyewitnesses misidentified the accused and due to their identification and in some cases the prosecution did not bring appear their main witnesses, due to not having enough representation they stay in prison without trial.

Overburdened an Inefficient Justice System

Pakistan's criminal justice system is having higher number of cases due to which not get trial timely it will impose burden on courts. This burden leads to wrongful convictions.

Another reason of wrongful conviction is the pressure of high courts of all provinces and their unit system, every judge has to decide the number of cases to get units. This system is also responsible for wrongful convictions. Though a good step is taken by high courts to provide free legal aid but, yet un-professionals and the officials selected for legal aid are not interested in it, it also increases wrongful convictions. The selection of the said legal heirs are based on recommendations.

Widespread of Police Misconduct and Forced Confessions

Police misconduct is another reason of wrongful conviction. The officers of police get conviction and they are guaranteed promotion on the basis of number of convictions. This guarantee boosts their misconduct and they will find out the more ways to increase it, just for the sake of promotion.

Objectives of the Study

The object is to stop the punishing of innocent people just because of the fault of system. This will suggest simple and helpful change to make justice system fair.

1. Finding of main reasons of wrongful convictions, including the weaknesses of investigation, forced confessions, not reliable evidence, bribery and lack of legal support.
2. To observe the impact of these conviction on individuals as well as on society, that how these convictions can harm the life of individuals and how their families suffer and how the trust of public is reduced.
3. To study the role of police, court, defense, and courts and their contributions and their role to overcome the problem.
4. To look at the legal protection provided to an individual by constitution, and how it can be protected.
5. To do the comparison of justice system of Pakistan with international standards, especially with the context of obligation of agreement of Human Rights like ICCPR.
6. To suggest the solution and reforms for decreasing of wrongful convictions.

Limitations of the Study

The study focused on these convictions but also have some limitations. Firstly, its reliance is on articles reports and case laws. The actual sources are ignored like the interview of the victim of these conviction, officials of the court including judges, lawyers, and police officials. The second limitation is the examination of recorded cases. Unreported and unpublished cases are not included in this. It is not completed without those unpublished cases. This focus of the study is to analyze the law, judgment and reports despite of statistical data. It makes is artificial instead of real. Despite of these limitations it provides a lot of solutions and valuable suggestion to overcome the wrongful convictions.

Research Questions

1. What are main causes which leads to wrongful conviction?
2. What are the effects of wrongful conviction on individual including their family?
3. What are the contributions of courts, lawyers and police officials to overcome the issue?
4. Are the current laws and procedures being enough to serve the individuals the right of fair trial?
5. Is Pakistan justice system can be compared with internal Human right standards
6. What reforms are needed to make the system fairer and more reliable?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study will focus on laws, judgments of the court, legal writings and some surways. But the primary source will be the constitution of Pakistan, (especially the Article 10-A which ask for Fair Trial) (Constitution of Pakistan, 1973, Article 10A (Right to Fair Trial). the code of criminal procedure, some of the important case laws, book relevant to the research, research articles, reports and reports of the Human Rights Commission.

Along with this another approach will also be applied and comparison will be done with other countries judicial system like USA and UK, the wrongful conviction case and how they are dealing it. The aim of this research is to collect the material from authentic sources and suggest reforms which are not just actionable, should also be acceptable and affordable. It will be the great step if the reforms are brought it will be having high impact on justice system of Pakistan.

Research Design

The research will follow multiple approaches like qualitative and analytical, but the main focus will be on laws, court judgment, and different research journals for the sake of understanding of the issue wrongful conviction in Pakistan.

Primary Sources

The primary source is none other than constitution of Pakistan, the procedure of criminal cases and judgments of superior courts, Provincial Superior courts and Federal Superior Court. The sources will provide the framework for the solution.

Secondary Source

The books, laws and articles report, and the studies of the progressive countries justice system is the secondary source. The Human Rights Commission of Pakistan reports and Amnesty international will also be included in secondary sources. Critical Analysis

The study will mainly focus on the reason of wrongful conviction in Pakistan. Such as...

- Police mostly relies on weak investigations along with their weak witnesses.
- Police get conviction through torture
- The lack of usage of forensic science in criminal case except in some cases.
- Lack of representation for poor accused persons.

DATA COLLECTION AND VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Data Collection

The whole research will rely on secondary sources like books, articles, judgments, governments reports, sunrays, reports of the well knows journal and online legal database. It will focus on the data which is collected before this research but unfortunately cannot be used effectively or ignored, so it is the aim of the research to collect it through references that how different countries adopt these methods they brought reforms and now a day they decrease the rate of wrongful convictions.

Variables of the Study

The main variables in this study are:

- Causes – poor prosecution along with their poor evidence, lack of use of forensic science and lack of legal defense.
- Impact –it is included on suffering of social, psychological and legal on victim of wrongful conviction. Including social, psychological, and legal consequences on innocent individuals.
- Legal reforms– steps should be taken to overcome the suffering of wrongful conviction or at least have a review method.

SAMPLING

The research will filter all the previous reports regarding this topic it will not be included on just some sunrays. It will choose the most accurate and nearer to reality data for the study which would be actionable (Shah, M. (2014).

Legal Documents

the judgments of superior courts, like Apex court of Pakistan, Superior Court of Baluchistan, superior Court of Sindh, Islamabad superior court, Lahore superior Court, superior court of Azad Kashmir and Peshawar superior Court. The Code of Criminal Procedure.

Reports and Studies

The Different reports of the different organization like The Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (HRCP), Amnesty International, will be used in different cases as in case where wrongful convictions occurred.

This type of sampling is most suitable because it focuses only on relevant and reliable sources, which will help in deeply understanding the problem and suggesting better reforms. Purposive sampling of wrongfully convicted individuals who have been currently being reviewed. A minimum of 15-20 interviews with people from diverse backgrounds (ethnicity, religion, socioeconomic status).

Interview Guide

Trial process:

- Can you describe the events that led to your conviction?
- Were there any issues with the evidence presented during your trial?
- Were you provided with adequate legal representation?
- Did you face any force during police interrogation or trial?

Research Analysis Tools

- This will be included in qualitative scale analysis some of which are mentioned below.
- Content Analysis: Judgments their readings and examination of the said wrongful convictions to find out the reasons behind problem (Khan, A. (2015)..
- Case Law Study: reviewing the judgments and court decisions to review the said judgment that how judges handled the case, is the right of fair trial under article 10-A is provided or not
- Comparative Study: the compare of justice system of Pakistan with progressive countries and their difference and strengths to overcome the issue through reforms.
- Doctrinal Method: by observing the procedure of Criminal case known as Code of criminal procedure and especially the evidence acts its weakness and how to strengthen is through amendments.

The above-mentioned tools will explain the research in great way and will suggest some good reforms as well.

Feasibility (Time, Resources, Availability)

The requirement of the research is easily available, so the research is possible and affordable as well. The resources are books of law, articles of research related to the same topic, case laws and reports of different organizations which are mentioned above. These reports can be found in university libraries, online legal databases. The reports of the well-known organization can be found on their official pages via internet it can be found. Those reports will provide very important and meaningful information in very accurate manner. In the light of these sources it will be easy to understand the main cause of wrongful conviction and reforms for overcoming of the issue.

In context of time management, the study is more realistic because there is not field work, we just have to review the written sources. It can be divided in to different steps, the primary step is to collect the data form primary sources like judgments of superior courts, like apex court of Pakistan, superior Court of Baluchistan, superior Court of Sindh, Islamabad superior court, Lahore superior Court, superior court of Azad Kashmir and Peshawar superior Court. The Code of Criminal Procedure. Then the next step is to review the secondary sources like articles and books, writing and their results. The research can be completed in period of time if planned will. The addition of the secondary sources like The Human Rights Commission of Pakistan reports and Amnesty international will be highly recommended.

Regarding resources

This research is affordable it does not require any big financial support. It can be done through basic niceties. The library, Printing service and internet comes in necessities. As most of the sources are available online and in libraries so there is no need of big expanses and it reduces the expense, which could be spent in case of non-availability. It is not just only affordable as the primary and secondary sources are utilized it is realistic.

The research will bring awareness in public regarding their rights. The wrongful convictions are the death of trust of public on all institutions especially court. The suggestion of the

better reforms can be a good step to improve the investigation, the training of the officials of the all institutions will boost their capacity and accountability will bound them to be limited in their place provided them by the constitution of Pakistan. It will contribute to knowledge and will be a better step in strengthening justice system in Pakistan.

CONCLUSION

The research highlighted the very important and serious issued present in our justice system. As there is a maxim that,

“Justice delayed is justice Denied”

But in our case the delays of justice are very usual, and no one is having any concern regarding that. Though police makers are not taking it seriously, but this gradual and slow breach of trust may convert in to the anarchy and people will not be having trust on state and its institutions. This research stresses that wrongful conviction is not the tragedy of an individuals it is also the reflection of the justice system and its weaknesses which shows clearly in mirror. It provides a chance to policy maker to bring reforms to sought out the problem. It also shows the comparison of the justice system of Pakistan with other progressive countries. In final thoughts it is very essential to mention that reforms are very necessary for the assuring of protection of human rights. Through all the suggestion given in research improvements can be brought in all area whether it is investigation methods, judicial procedure, provision of legal aid. All the issues can be improved through these reforms. It will not just stop the wrongful conviction but will also boost up the trust of the people on institutions of the state, preferably on legal system.

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